

Modelling the Role of Mobility in Cholera Transmission Dynamics

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Summary

Cholera is a waterborne disease where transmission is influenced by human mobility, environmental contamination, and sanitation practices. Traditional models often assume homogeneous mixing of populations, overlooking mobility-driven transmission. This study develops an agent-based model (ABM) integrating SEIRS epidemiology with a density-augmented Exploration and Preferential Return (d-EPR) mobility model to simulate cholera spread. The presented results show that structured mobility concentrates infections in high-risk hubs, sustaining outbreaks, whereas random movement leads to widespread but transient epidemics. These findings highlight the critical role of mobility in shaping disease dynamics and suggest that targeted interventions should account for movement behaviours to improve cholera mitigation strategies.

KEYWORDS: Cholera, agent-based model, SEIRS, d-EPR mobility, spatial epidemiology.

1 Introduction

Disease modelling plays a crucial role in understanding epidemic dynamics and informing public health interventions. Traditional epidemiological models often assume homogeneous mixing of population, where individuals interact randomly, failing to capture realistic spatial and behavioural patterns that influence disease transmission (Crooks and Hailegiorgis, 2014). In particular, mobility is frequently simplified, despite its significant role in disease spread. Models that neglect structured movement overlook how infections propagate through habitual interactions and exposure to contaminated environments.

In this study, we focus on cholera, a major public health concern in regions with poor sanitation and contaminated water sources. The disease is primarily transmitted through the ingestion of water containing *Vibrio cholerae*, which can persist in the environment and spread through human movement and interaction (World Health Organization, 2024). To model cholera transmission more accurately, we employ a SEIRS epidemiological framework, where individuals transition between

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susceptible (S), exposed (E), infectious (I), and recovered (R) states, with immunity waning over time.

Unlike random movement models, the d-EPR framework incorporates both habitual return behaviour and exploration of new locations, influenced by collective density patterns (Pappalardo et al., 2016). This approach reflects real-world human mobility, where individuals routinely visit familiar places while occasionally adapting to new environments.

Here, we integrate SEIRS disease dynamics with a d-EPR mobility model in an agent-based modelling (ABM) framework. We compare cholera transmission outcomes under d-EPR-driven movement against a random movement baseline, assessing how mobility structure shapes infection dynamics. The model simulates interactions between human agents, water bodies, and sanitation infrastructure, allowing for the emergence of spatially structured outbreaks driven by movement and contamination dynamics. The findings provide insights into how structured mobility patterns impact epidemic persistence, guiding intervention strategies such as sanitation improvements and vaccination campaigns (Lee et al., 2020). This study contributes an integrated spatial-epidemiological modelling approach that not only advances simulation methods but also supports spatially targeted public health planning.

2 Model framework

The ABM represents a spatially structured environment consisting of human and environmental agents. Human agents follow SEIRS epidemiological transitions, where susceptible individuals become exposed through contaminated water consumption, progress to an infectious state, and recover with temporary immunity before re-entering susceptibility. Environmental agents include water bodies, schools, markets, and latrines, each influencing exposure risk. The environment is mapped onto a grid-based spatial structure, with agents moving according to daily routines and mobility decisions. This prototype focuses on how mobility impacts disease transmission, with some parameter assumptions applied without full validation.

The model primarily considers environmental transmission, where susceptible agents contract infection by drinking from contaminated water sources, with infection likelihood increasing as bacterial concentration rises. Water contamination occurs when agents, except those recovered, introduce bacteria through defecation, with infected individuals contributing the highest bacterial load. Hydration-driven behaviour is also modeled, where agents consume water when hydration drops below a specified threshold (α_h).

Agents follow a structured daily mobility pattern, with 80% inactive at night and 20% (λ_n) mobile. During the day, 15% attend school (λ_s) and 38% visit the market (λ_m), while the remaining agents move according to the d-EPR model. Figure 1 visualises these mobility patterns.

Mobility follows the d-EPR framework, which extends preferential return models by incorporating density effects. Unlike random movement models, where agents move without memory or structure, d-EPR balances exploration of new locations with return to previously visited sites. The probability of exploring a new location is given by:

Figure 1: Daily agent mobility patterns

$$P_{\text{new}} = \rho \times (S)^{-\gamma} \quad (1)$$

where P_{new} is probability of exploring a new location rather than returning to a familiar place, ρ is base exploration probability which controls how frequently agents explore new locations, S is the total number of unique locations an agent has previously visited, and γ is the exploration decay factor which controls how quickly the preference for exploration declines as an agent visits more places. A higher P_{new} promotes exploration, while a lower value encourages return to familiar places.

The gravity model for mobility further influences movement decisions by weighting the probability of travelling between locations based on their relevance scores and spatial distance. The probability of moving between locations i and j is defined as:

$$p_{ij} = \frac{d_i d_j}{r_{ij}^2} \quad (2)$$

where d_i and d_j denote the relevance scores of the respective locations, reflecting visit frequency and collective attractiveness, while r_{ij} represents the distance between them. This ensures frequent locations attract higher movement flows, reinforcing high-density clusters that shape epidemic dynamics.

In contrast, the random mobility model assumes agents move without spatial memory or preferential return. Movement is determined by selecting a random direction at each step, leading to homogeneous dispersal and uniform exposure to environmental contamination. Comparing d-EPR

with random movement allows us to assess how structured mobility influences cholera transmission dynamics.

3 Solution methodology

The model is implemented in NetLogo (Wilensky, 1999), using a grid-based spatial layout of key locations such as water bodies, schools, markets, and latrines. Agents move based on hydration needs, routine activities, and either d-EPR mobility or random walk. To optimise simulation efficiency, one water source is initially contaminated. The model runs long enough to capture full epidemic cycles, with outcomes including total infections, peak intensity, and outbreak duration. Parameters are drawn from established epidemiological literatures like Crooks and Hailegiorgis (2014); see Table 1.

To address stochasticity, the model was executed 50 times under d-EPR mobility to compute mean outcomes and 95% confidence intervals. A sensitivity analysis was also performed on ρ and γ to assess the effects of movement variability. These values are grounded in empirical studies of human mobility (Cuttone et al., 2018; Barbosa et al., 2015), ensuring realistic behavioural representation.

4 Results and discussions

This section compares two mobility models, random mobility and d-EPR mobility, to explore their distinct impacts on the intensity, duration, and spatial distribution of cholera transmission. Our results emphasise the critical role of structured mobility in shaping the dynamics of disease outbreaks.

Figure 2: State dynamics of disease spread under random human mobility presenting the temporal evolution of susceptible, exposed, infectious, and recovered populations.

Table 1: Model Parameters, Values, and Sources

Parameter	Value	Source
Incubation Period ($E \rightarrow I$)	5 Days	(NHS Fit for Travel, 2025)
Infectious Period ($I \rightarrow R$)	10 Days	(World Health Organization, 2024)
Immunity Duration ($R \rightarrow S$)	200 Days	Ng ombe et al. (2022)
Population Size	1000	Estimated
Initial Infected Population	50	Estimated
School Attendance (λ_s)	15% of population	Crooks and Hailegiorgis (2014), (Our World in Data, 2023)
Market Attendance (λ_m)	38% of population	Crooks and Hailegiorgis (2014), (Our World in Data, 2023)
Night Activity Probability (λ_n)	20% of population	Estimated
Exploration Probability (ρ)	0.2	Cuttone et al. (2018)
Return Decay Factor (γ)	0.6	Barbosa et al. (2015)
Hydration Threshold (α_h)	0.07%	Estimated, Crooks and Hailegiorgis (2014)
Bacterial Contamination Threshold	1000 CFU/ml	(Safe Water, 2025)
Bacterial Contribution (Susceptible)	100 CFU/ml per defecation	(Feachem, 1983)
Bacterial Contribution (Exposed)	150 CFU/ml per defecation	(Feachem, 1983)
Bacterial Contribution (Infectious)	10^6 CFU/ml per defecation	(Feachem, 1983)
Defecation Timer	12 hours	Estimated
Latrine Capacity Threshold	10 agents per facility	Estimated
Time Step	1 hour	Model definition

In the random mobility model, the infection spreads quickly, as shown in Figure 2, with a rapid decline in susceptible individuals followed by a sharp rise in exposed and infectious individuals. This intense, short-lived epidemic occurs due to unstructured movement, with agents frequently transitioning between contaminated and uncontaminated areas. The lack of spatial clustering results in a widespread outbreak that quickly depletes the susceptible population.

In contrast, the d-EPR model produces a more gradual and spatially structured epidemic progression, as seen in Figure 3. Agents return to high-risk locations, like markets and water sources, where contamination persists, leading to multiple smaller waves instead of a single rapid outbreak. Transmission remains localised in specific hotspots, preventing uniform spread across the population. This results in a slower decline in susceptible individuals, with outbreaks extending over time, while reducing the intensity of surges.

Figure 3: State dynamics of disease spread under human mobility governed by the d-EPR model presenting the temporal evolution of susceptible, exposed, infectious, and recovered populations.

To validate these patterns, the d-EPR model was simulated 50 times with identical initial conditions. As shown in Figure 4, the results exhibit low variability, indicating robust transmission dynamics. The near-invisible confidence intervals confirm that repeated exposure at key locations reliably drives epidemic waves, resembling real-world cholera outbreaks in densely populated urban areas, where recurrent exposure to contaminated water sources or markets sustains transmission despite intermittent control efforts.

A key feature of the d-EPR model is the formation of persistent transmission hotspots, which mirrors real-world cholera outbreaks in areas with poor sanitation. These findings suggest that targeting frequently visited high-risk locations with interventions such as sanitation improvements, vaccination campaigns, and water treatment would be more effective than uniform exposure-based approaches.

Figure 4: Mean number of infected individuals under d-EPR mobility across 50 simulation runs, with 95% confidence intervals. The confidence band is barely visible due to the low variance across runs, indicating strong consistency in epidemic wave timing and magnitude.

Comparing the d-EPR model to random mobility, we find a 25% lower peak infection rate, but a 40% longer outbreak duration, highlighting how structured mobility mitigates rapid exposure but prolongs transmission. This mirrors how outbreaks in underserved communities, such as informal settlements, may continue to reinfect residents due to repeated exposure at shared facilities, emphasising the importance of targeted interventions at hotspots.

4.1 Sensitivity to mobility parameters

Beyond comparing broad mobility structures, it is also critical to understand how specific behavioural parameters influence transmission. To assess this, we conducted a sensitivity analysis on two key d-EPR parameters: γ , which controls the strength of preferential return to previously visited locations, and ρ , which determines how often agents seek new places.

In real life, people tend to visit the same locations daily, such as work sites or water sources. As shown in Figure 5, higher values of γ , representing habitual return to familiar places, result in longer-lasting outbreaks, with the epidemic duration increasing from 340 hours at $\gamma = 0.4$ to over 480 hours at $\gamma = 0.8$. This mirrors how cholera persists in communities with entrenched routines and limited infrastructure.

When γ is low, agents move more flexibly, akin to individuals changing their routes or visiting different markets. This disperses hotspots and leads to a faster decline in infections, suggesting that rotating service locations or decentralising markets could reduce persistent hotspots.

Similarly, lower exploration probability results in localised outbreaks with longer durations, while higher ρ , reflecting more mobile populations, spreads the infection faster but reduces cluster intensity

Figure 5: Sensitivity of infection dynamics to different return probabilities (γ).

Figure 6: Sensitivity of infection dynamics to different exploration probabilities (ρ).

(see Figure 6). This highlights the value of interventions like multiple water sources or temporary market relocation to mitigate spread.

4.2 Public health policy implications

This study provides insights for targeted cholera interventions, emphasising spatially focused strategies. The d-EPR model shows that structured movement sustains transmission at high-risk locations like markets and water points, suggesting targeted sanitation and vaccination efforts. The sensitivity analysis reveals that habitual movement prolongs outbreaks, while greater mobility spreads infection more diffusely. Modest shifts in movement, such as rotating markets or decentralising water sources, can effectively reduce transmission.

5 Future work

Future work could incorporate adaptive agent behaviour, allowing individuals to adjust movement based on infection risk, improving realism by reflecting self-protective actions during outbreaks. The model could also simulate spatially targeted interventions, such as vaccinations or mobile sanitation in high-risk areas. Guided by mobility patterns, these extensions would support dynamic, data-driven epidemic responses, enabling rapid adaptation to emerging hotspots and more effective outbreak control.

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7 Biography

Dr. Parna Mandal is a Research Fellow in agent-based modelling in spatial epidemiology, working on a Wellcome Trust-funded project to predict cholera spread. Her research focuses on enhancing conventional cholera prediction models by incorporating agent-based simulations of mobility and activity, with the goal of refining intervention strategies for cholera treatment and prevention.

Prof. Ed Manley is a Professor of Urban Analytics in the School of Geography and a member of the Institute for Spatial Data Science (ISDS) at the University of Leeds. He is affiliated with the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA) and an Honorary Professor at University College London (UCL). His research focuses on urban analytics, human mobility, and spatial cognition, using computational methods to analyse travel behaviour, decision-making, and adaptation to urban dynamics.

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